

1 **NACA is selectively activated during the first cell division of the human embryo.**

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6 We studied gene expression in the human embryo immediately after fertilization and zygotic activation and
7 at the first cell division from 1-cell to 2-cell stage. We describe here discovery/identification of the nascent
8 polypeptide-associated complex alpha subunit *NACA* as a zygotic cell factor required or important during
9 the first cell division of the fertilized human embryo.

10 Citation

11 1. Liu, Y., Hu, Y., Li, X., Niu, L. and Teng, M., 2010. The crystal structure of the human nascent
12 polypeptide-associated complex domain reveals a nucleic acid-binding region on the *NACA* subunit.
13 *Biochemistry*, 49(13), pp.2890-2896.
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